

1 **Inbreeding in French dairy sheep.** Rodríguez-Ramilo. The genetic diversity of five selected
2 French dairy sheep subpopulations and breeds is quantified by three different methods
3 (pedigree, SNP-by-SNP and runs of homozygosity) using a medium-density SNP chip. The
4 effect of factors defining runs of homozygosity is also assessed. Estimates of effective
5 population size were above 200 in Lacaune subpopulations and below 200 in Basco-
6 Béarnaise, Manech Tête Noire and Manech Tête Rousse breeds. Factors defining runs of
7 homozygosity do not change much the results unless extreme values are considered, although
8 further research on ROH-based inbreeding is still required.

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INBREEDING IN FRENCH DAIRY SHEEP

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14 **Inbreeding and effective population size in French dairy sheep: comparison between**
15 **genomic and pedigree estimates**

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ABSTRACT

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27 Before availability of dense SNP data, genetic diversity has been characterised and managed
28 with pedigree-based information. Besides this classical approach, two methodologies have
29 also been proposed in the last years to characterise and manage diversity from dense SNP
30 (Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms) data, which include the SNP-by-SNP approach and the
31 alternative based on ROH (Runs Of Homozygosity). The establishment of criteria to identify
32 ROH is a current constraint in the literature dealing with ROH. The objective of this study is,
33 using a medium-density SNP chip, to quantify by three different methods (pedigree, SNP-by-
34 SNP and ROH) the genetic diversity on five selected French dairy sheep subpopulations and
35 breeds, and to assess the effect of the definition of ROH on these estimates. The data set
36 available included individuals from the breeds Basco-Béarnaise (BB), Manech Tête Noire
37 (MTN), Manech Tête Rousse (MTR), and two subpopulations of Lacaune: Lacaune
38 Confederation (LACCon) and Lacaune Ovitest (LACOvi). Animals were genotyped with the
39 Illumina OvineSNP50 BeadChip. After filtering, the genomic data included 38,287 autosomal
40 SNP and 8,700 individuals, which comprised 72,803 animals in the pedigree. The results
41 indicate that no significant differences were observed in N_e estimates obtained from pedigree
42 or genomic (SNP-by-SNP or ROH) information. In general, estimates of N_e were above 200
43 in LACCon and LACOvi subpopulations and below 200 in BB, MTN and MTR breeds. The
44 minimum length that constituted a ROH, the minimum number of SNP that constituted a
45 ROH, the minimum density and the maximum distance allowed between two homozygous
46 SNP are ROH defining factors with important implications in the estimation of the rate of
47 inbreeding. ROH-based rates of inbreeding in concordance to those obtained from pedigree
48 information require a specific set of values. This particular set of values is different to that

49 identified to obtain ROH-based rates of inbreeding similar to those obtained on a SNP-by-
50 SNP basis. Factors to define ROH do not change much the results unless extreme values are
51 considered, although further research on ROH-based inbreeding is still required.

52

53 **Key Words:** run of homozygosity, rate of inbreeding, effective population size

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55

INTRODUCTION

56

57

58 The preservation of genetic diversity is usually achieved by maximising the effective
59 population size, or equivalently, by minimising the rate of inbreeding in a population.

60 Genomic selection can reduce the rate of inbreeding per generation but can lead to a higher
61 rate of inbreeding per year (Daetwyler et al., 2007). Such increase in the rate of inbreeding
62 can result in lower genetic diversity, lower response to selection and a higher exposure of
63 deleterious alleles (Curik et al., 2014). For this reason, controlling the rate of inbreeding is an
64 important goal in breeding programs.

65

66 Prior to the widespread availability of dense SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms) data,
67 genetic diversity has been characterised and managed with pedigree-based inbreeding
68 estimates. This approximation refers to the proportion of the genome that is expected to be
69 identical by descent (IBD). However, this pedigree-based approach has several constraints.
70 First, pedigree completeness and quality are essential (Oliehoek and Bijma, 2009). Second,
71 pedigree information does not take into account, neither Mendelian sampling variation (Hill
72 and Weir, 2011), nor linkage disequilibrium caused by selection (e.g. Smith and Haigh,
73 1974).

74

75 The realised proportion of the genome that two individuals share can be more accurately
76 estimated from genome-based information than from pedigree-based information (Howard et
77 al., 2017). Two alternatives have been proposed to characterise and manage diversity from
78 dense SNP data. The first is the SNP-by-SNP approach (e. g. VanRaden, 2008). It involves
79 the estimation of the alleles that are identical by state (IBS) for each individual SNP.

80 Consequently, it captures relationships caused by common ancestors going back to a base
81 population where all alleles are supposed to be unique. The second is the segment-based
82 approach (e. g. McQuillan et al., 2008), which considers IBS segments, rather than individual
83 SNP. The segments of homozygous genotypes are called runs of homozygosity (ROH). ROH-
84 based inbreeding estimates could capture the relatedness between nominally unrelated
85 founders of the pedigree (Peripolli et al., 2017), consider the stochastic mechanism of
86 recombination (Keller et al., 2011), and also consider the linkage disequilibrium between loci
87 caused by selection (Curik et al., 2002). ROH basically could arise due to autozygosity, where
88 the same chromosomal segment has been passed to an offspring from parents who inherited it
89 from a common ancestor (Broman and Weber, 1999). Accordingly, ROH with ancient origin
90 are expected to be shorter, because recombination from repeated meioses breaks up IBD
91 segments. On the other hand, ROH due to recent inbreeding are expected to be longer because
92 the probability of breaking up IBD segments from recombination is reduced.

93

94 There is a need to establish consistent and reproducible criteria for identifying and
95 quantifying ROH. The comparison between studies is challenging because there is a high
96 inconsistency among the criteria used to identify ROH both within and also between species
97 (Ku et al., 2011; Peripolli et al., 2017). This lack of standard criteria for identifying ROH
98 enhances the probability of introducing bias on ROH-based inbreeding estimates.

99 Accordingly, some parameters and thresholds imposed during the sequence analysis can
100 affect ROH identification (Howrigan et al., 2011). Also pruning SNP that show low minor
101 allele frequency, that deviate from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, or showing high linkage
102 disequilibrium can influence ROH characterisation (Arbrechtsen et al., 2010). Likewise, the
103 number of heterozygous genotypes and the SNP chip density also can influence ROH

104 identification in cattle (Purfield et al., 2012; Ferenčaković et al., 2013; Mastrangelo et al.,
105 2016). Several studies have evaluated ROH across all major livestock species (see Peripolli et
106 al., 2017 for a revision). However, further exploration is desirable to better understand the
107 criteria for estimating ROH-based inbreeding.

108

109 Selection of French dairy sheep has been implemented for each local breed separately. The
110 largest breed is the Lacaune, which consists of two subpopulations: Lacaune Confederation
111 (LACCon) and Lacaune Ovitest (LACOvi). The second population is located in the Western
112 Pyrenees mountains, and it consists of three breeds: Manech Tête Rousse (MTR), Manech
113 Tête Noire (MTN) and Basco-Béarnaise (BB). Breeding programs, started in the sixties, are
114 now clearly profitable (Larroque et al., 2014) and genomic selection is being established
115 (Legarra et al., 2014). Accordingly, genomic selection should include genomic management
116 of inbreeding (Sonnesson et al., 2012). However, it is still unclear how to implement genomic
117 management of diversity within these breeds.

118

119 The objectives of this study are the following. First, to quantify the genetic diversity in five
120 selected French sheep subpopulations and breeds with several pedigree- and marker-based
121 methods and to compare the existing results in terms of rate of inbreeding and on effective
122 population size. Second, to establish the robustness of ROH-based measures of inbreeding to
123 the criteria used to define a ROH. All using a medium-density SNP chip.

124

125

MATERIALS AND METHODS

126

127 *Data*

128

129 Rams were genotyped with the OvineSNP50 BeadChip (Illumina Inc., San Diego, CA).

130 Supplementary Figure 1 shows the distribution of progeny-tested rams genotyped per year of

131 birth. The genotyped animals in BB breed were born between 1999 and 2008, between 1996

132 and 2007 in MTN breed, between 1999 and 2009 in MTR breed, between 1996 and 2012 in

133 LACCon subpopulation, and between 1999 and 2012 in LACovi subpopulation.

134

135 SNP quality control included the absence of parent-offspring Mendelian segregation

136 incompatibilities ($< 3\%$), SNP call rate ($> 97\%$) and large deviations from Hardy-Weinberg

137 equilibrium (SNP with $P < 10^{-6}$ were discarded) (see Baloché et al., 2014 and Legarra et al.,

138 2014 for more details). The final dataset included 38,287 autosomal SNP and 8,700

139 genotyped animals. The pedigree data set was constructed with all known ancestors of the

140 genotyped individuals and comprised 72,803 animals, all breeds merged. Table 1 shows per

141 subpopulation and breed the number of genotyped animals, the individuals included in the

142 pedigree and the equivalent number of complete generations.

143

144 - Table 1 -

145

146 ***Pedigree-based inbreeding estimates***

147

148 The pedigree-based inbreeding estimates (F_{PED}) of the genotyped individuals were obtained

149 using the software PEDIG (Boichard, 2002) with the option that implements the algorithm of

150 Meuwissen and Luo (1992). The generation interval was calculated also using PEDIG and

151 was 4.95, 4.51, 4.20, 3.61 and 3.55 for BB, MTN, MTR, LACCon and LACovi, respectively,
152 in accordance with previous estimates (Larroque et al., 2014).

153

154 ***SNP-by-SNP inbreeding estimates***

155

156 Following the logic of Malécot (1948), IBS relationships are twice the probability that two
157 alleles taken at random, one per individual, are identical. For one individual with itself the
158 sampling is with replacement, and the relationship reduces to 1 + the probability that one
159 allele is identical to the other one. Thus, the inbreeding coefficient of individual i based on
160 individual SNP (F_{SNP_i}) is simply the probability that the two alleles are identical, measured
161 across the genome, and was equal to the proportion of typed loci at which this individual is
162 homozygous (Silió et al., 2013).

163

164 ***ROH-based inbreeding estimates***

165

166 Runs of homozygosity are long, uninterrupted stretches of homozygous genotypes
167 (McQuillan et al., 2008). More specifically, the inbreeding estimator, F_{ROH} , is the proportion
168 of the genome that is in ROH. For individual i , F_{ROH_i} was calculated as

169

$$170 \quad F_{ROH_i} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_{ROH_i}} l_{ROH_{ik}}}{l_g},$$

171

172 where n_{ROH_i} is the total number of ROH in individual i , $l_{ROH_{ik}}$ is the length of the k^{th} ROH
173 in individual i in base pairs and l_g is the length of the genome in base pairs (in the data set
174 analysed in the present study is 2,438,309,318 bp). An example of ROH is shown in Figure 1.

175

176 - Figure 1 -

177

178 There are six criteria for identifying a ROH, which consider the information provided by the
179 SNP itself (i. e. homozygous, heterozygous or missing genotype) and its map position in the
180 chromosome. These six criteria are: (i) the minimum length in Mb that constituted a ROH, (ii)
181 the minimum number of SNP that constituted a ROH, (iii) the minimum density: at least 1
182 SNP every this distance of Kb, (iv) the maximum distance allowed between two consecutive
183 homozygous SNP in Mb, (v) the maximum number of missing genotypes allowed and (vi) the
184 maximum number of heterozygous genotypes permitted within a particular ROH. Table 2
185 shows the different values tested for each ROH defining factor and their default values (based
186 on Peripolli et al., 2017).

187

188 - Table 2 -

189

190 ***Rate of inbreeding and effective population size***

191

192 Rates of inbreeding per year ($\Delta F_{PED_{year}}$, $\Delta F_{SNP_{year}}$, and $\Delta F_{ROH_{year}}$) were computed from the
193 regression coefficient of the inbreeding coefficient for each individual on the year of birth
194 taking into account the 8,700 animals. Rates of inbreeding per generation (ΔF_{PED} , ΔF_{SNP} , and

195 ΔF_{ROH}) were calculated by multiplying the rates of inbreeding per year by the generation
 196 interval (L). Finally, estimates of effective population size were obtained from the rate of
 197 inbreeding per generation as $N_{ePED} = 1 / 2\Delta F_{PED}$, $N_{eSNP} = 1 / 2\Delta F_{SNP}$ and $N_{eROH} = 1 / 2\Delta F_{ROH}$
 198 (Falconer and Mackay, 1996). Confidence intervals for effective population sizes were
 199 obtained from the standard error of the rates of inbreeding per year, e. g., the estimator of

200 N_{eSNP} is $1 / 2L\Delta F_{SNP_{year}}$ and its confidence interval is $\frac{1}{2L \left[\Delta F_{SNP_{year}} \pm 1.96s.e.(\Delta F_{SNP_{year}}) \right]}$.

201

202

RESULTS

203

Comparison of pedigree- and genome-based inbreeding estimators

205

206 In this section the default values used for identifying a ROH were established as: (i) the
 207 minimum length that constituted a ROH was 4 Mb, (ii) the minimum number of SNP was 30,
 208 (iii) the minimum density was 1 SNP per 100 Kb, (iv) the maximum distance allowed
 209 between two consecutive homozygous SNP in a run was 1 Mb, (v) a maximum of two
 210 missing genotypes and (vi) one heterozygous genotype within a particular ROH were
 211 permitted. These default values were highlighted in bold in Table 2.

212

213 Table 3 shows the average inbreeding values for each evaluated subpopulation and breed.
 214 ROH-based inbreeding estimates were slightly higher than those obtained from pedigree-
 215 based information. Inbreeding estimates obtained on a SNP-by-SNP basis (IBS) result in
 216 higher values than other estimators because they cannot distinguish between IBD and IBS.

217 The difference is roughly a constant, e. g. for a single locus $IBS = IBD + (1 - IBD)(p^2 + q^2)$

218 that vanishes when computing the rates of inbreeding (Toro et al., 2011). The lowest values of
219 inbreeding were observed in LACCon subpopulation. In addition, the highest values of
220 inbreeding were obtained for LACOvi subpopulation (F_{PED}) and MTN breed (F_{SNP} and F_{ROH}).

221

222 - Table 3 -

223

224 The correlation coefficient between the inbreeding estimates is shown in Table 4. For all the
225 evaluated subpopulations and breeds the correlation coefficient between pedigree- and
226 genomic-based inbreeding estimates is moderate (ranged between 0.38 and 0.58). The highest
227 correlation was observed between both genomic inbreeding estimates (ranged between 0.78
228 and 0.88). Moreover, the lowest correlation was observed between F_{PED} and F_{ROH} , with the
229 exception of MTR breed, where the lowest correlation was observed between F_{PED} and F_{SNP} .
230 Differences are, however, very small.

231

232 - Table 4 -

233

234 The rate of inbreeding per generation is also shown in Table 3 for each evaluated
235 subpopulation and breed. Similar estimates of rate of inbreeding were obtained both with
236 pedigree- and genomic-based information, in contrast to the average inbreeding estimates.
237 The highest values were observed for ΔF_{PED} (in BB, MTN and LACOvi) and ΔF_{ROH} (in
238 MTR and LACCon). The lowest values of rate of inbreeding were obtained with ΔF_{SNP} ,
239 except for LACOvi, where the lowest values were also observed with ΔF_{ROH} . For Lacaune,
240 values of ΔF are consistent with the three methods. This is not the case for BB, MTN and
241 MTR, where ΔF_{SNP} are consistently lowest.

242

243 Table 3 also shows estimates of effective population size with confidence intervals. The
244 lowest values of effective population size were obtained from ΔF_{PED} (in BB, MTN and
245 LACOvi) and ΔF_{ROH} (in MTR and LACCon). The highest values of effective population size
246 were observed with ΔF_{SNP} , except for LACOvi, where the highest values were also observed
247 with ΔF_{ROH} . The three rates of inbreeding agree ranking subpopulations and breeds by
248 effective population size. In order of decreasing N_e , the breeds and subpopulations were
249 LACOvi, LACCon, MTR, MTN and BB. The only exception was observed with ΔF_{PED} ,
250 which inverted LACCon and LACOvi. In general, N_e estimates were above 200 in LACCon
251 and LACOvi subpopulations, and below 200 in BB, MTN and MTR breeds. However, no
252 significant differences were observed in the estimates of N_e obtained from the three evaluated
253 inbreeding estimates. This highlights the agreement between pedigree-based and SNP-by-
254 SNP estimates of inbreeding with those obtained from ROH with the default values.

255

256 *Effect on estimates of factors defining ROH*

257

258 In the evaluation of each ROH defining factor, the other five ROH defining factors remained
259 with the default value highlighted in bold in Table 2.

260

261 Figures 2 – 3 and supplementary Figure 2 show the evolution of the rate of inbreeding in all
262 evaluated breeds and subpopulations for each ROH defining factor. The six evaluated factors
263 showed, in general, the same behaviour independently of the tested subpopulation or breed.
264 Four ROH defining factors have implications on the rate of inbreeding. These factors are: (i)

265 the minimum length that constituted a ROH, (ii) the minimum number of SNP that constituted
266 a ROH, (iii) the minimum density (at least 1 SNP every some specific number of bases) and
267 (iv) the maximum distance allowed between two consecutive homozygous SNP. Figure 2
268 shows that if the minimum length that constituted a ROH is equal or lower than 4 Mb (which
269 could probably reflect ancient inbreeding), ΔF_{ROH} are, in general, in concordance with ΔF_{PED}
270 . However, if the minimum length that constituted a ROH is higher than 4 Mb (which could
271 probably reflect more recent inbreeding), ΔF_{ROH} are close to ΔF_{SNP} . In addition, reduced
272 ROH lengths provided higher rates of inbreeding than greater ROH lengths. Accordingly,
273 ΔF_{ROH} obtained with ROH of ≤ 80 SNP are consistent with ΔF_{PED} , and ΔF_{ROH} estimated
274 from ROH of more than 80 SNP are, overall, similar to ΔF_{SNP} . The ΔF_{ROH} assessed with a
275 minimum density equal or lower than 1 SNP every 90 Kb is close to ΔF_{SNP} , and the ΔF_{ROH}
276 estimated with a minimum density higher than 1 SNP every 90 Kb is close to ΔF_{PED} . And
277 finally, a maximum distance between two homozygous SNP higher than 0.3 Mb makes that
278 ΔF_{ROH} agrees with ΔF_{PED} , and equal or lower to 0.3 Mb makes that ΔF_{ROH} matches with
279 ΔF_{SNP} (Figure 3).

280

281 Rates of inbreeding higher than those obtained with ROH default values have implications on
282 the estimation of diversity because a ΔF of 0.1% means that 0.1 percent of heterozygosity is
283 lost, and the actual constraints on management of inbreeding (e. g. using optimal
284 contributions) are typically based on ΔF (Meuwissen, 1997; Sonnesson et al., 2012). Thus,
285 different factors for ROH will lead to dissimilar ΔF_{ROH} . This will lead to diverse selection
286 decisions with more or less emphasis on genetic diversity.

287

288 Two ROH defining factors have generally no consequences on the estimation of the rate of
289 inbreeding across the evaluated subpopulations and breeds. These two factors are: (i) the
290 maximum number of missing genotypes allowed and (ii) the maximum number of
291 heterozygous permitted (Supplementary Figure 2).

292

293 - Figures 2 and 3 -

294

295 The ranking of subpopulations and breeds regarding the rate of inbreeding is the same when
296 evaluating the six ROH defining factors, where BB has the highest ΔF followed by MTN,
297 MTR, LACCon and finally LACovi. This ranking is only disrupted when the minimum
298 length that constituted a ROH is higher than 10 Mb, and when the minimum number of SNP
299 is higher than 300, probably due to the difficulty to find these types of ROH, and
300 consequently ROH-based inbreeding might be close to 0.

301

302

DISCUSSION

303

304 Inbreeding happens when an individual inherits chromosomal fragments that are IBD from
305 both parents, leading to faster allele fixation, reduction of additive genetic variance (in
306 principle), inbreeding depression and a decline in the response to selection (Kristensen and
307 Sorensen, 2005). Traditionally, inbreeding coefficients have been estimated using known
308 pedigrees (Wright, 1922). Inspired by the pedigree-based inbreeding coefficients, Caballero
309 and Toro (2002) proposed to estimate inbreeding on a SNP-by-SNP basis where each SNP is
310 considered individually. An alternative way to estimate inbreeding coefficients is to determine

311 the IBD probability of chromosome segments (ROH) instead of each SNP individually
312 (Howard et al., 2017).
313
314 Inbreeding coefficients evaluated in the present study are defined in relation to the base
315 population. In F_{PED} it is relative to the pedigree depth. In F_{ROH} it is dependent on the ROH
316 length. Finally, in F_{SNP} it is relative to Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. Thus, some differences
317 arise from the different definitions. F_{PED} estimates were lower than F_{SNP} and F_{ROH} , suggesting
318 that F_{PED} may possibly be underestimating inbreeding. This can be explained considering that
319 F_{PED} is an expectation and there is variability around this expectation (Keller et al., 2011).
320 More exactly, at one locus, the true inbreeding based on IBD has an expected value of F_{PED}
321 and a variance of $F_{PED}(1 - F_{PED})$ (García-Cortés et al., 2013). In addition, when calculating
322 F_{PED} it is assumed that founder animals are unrelated. This assumption may also lead to the
323 underestimation of F_{PED} if the recorded pedigree is not deep enough (depth of pedigree is very
324 heterogeneous in sheep breeds as shown in Table 1), is incomplete or there are some errors
325 due to misidentification (8% in these sheep breeds Tortereau et al., 2017), and incorrect
326 recording. Also F_{PED} assumes that the loci are neutral, so it does not consider loci submitted
327 to selection. As pedigree information has been used extensively to measure the proportion of
328 the genome that is IBD, the relatively moderate correlation between F_{PED} and F_{ROH} supports
329 that F_{ROH} can be used to predict IBD in sheep populations (Purfield et al., 2017). Accordingly,
330 similar correlations between F_{PED} and F_{ROH} were previously reported in cattle populations
331 (Zhang et al., 2015). However, this correlation depends on the minimum length that constitute
332 a ROH. For example, Silió et al. (2013) indicated a correlation between F_{PED} and F_{ROH} longer
333 than 1 Mb and F_{ROH} longer than 5 Mb of 0.78 and 0.82, respectively.
334

335 The absolute value of the inbreeding coefficient is not a valuable alternative to consider
336 whether there is too much inbreeding or not because is affected by several factors as (i) the
337 number of generations considered, (ii) if markers are used, (iii) the allele frequency spectrum
338 of those markers or (iv) factors defining ROH. The rate of inbreeding is a better criterion to
339 handle the inbreeding management and it translates into the effective size of a population
340 (Meuwissen et al., 2018).

341
342 Sheep have kept a considerable level of genetic diversity. The estimates of effective
343 population size showed in this study are similar to those previously reported in the same
344 breeds (Larroque et al., 2014) and also in other comparable sheep breeds (Li et al., 2009;
345 García-Gómez et al., 2012; Kijas et al., 2012; Al-Mamun et al., 2015; Beynon et al., 2015;
346 Chitneedi et al., 2017; Mastrangelo et al., 2017a, b; Purfield et al., 2017). An effective
347 population size smaller than 100 could compromise the long-term viability of the population
348 (Meuwissen, 2009). However, although estimated N_e are widely used, its estimation is
349 remarkably complex (Wang, 2005) and assumptions are generally not accomplished (Hayes et
350 al., 2003).

351
352 ROH have been studied in humans (e. g. Broman and Weber, 1999; Gibson et al., 2006;
353 Lencz et al., 2007; Curtis et al., 2008; McQuillan et al., 2008), cattle (e. g. Ferenčaković et al.,
354 2011; Purfield et al., 2012; Bjelland et al., 2013; Mastrangelo et al., 2016) and pigs (e. g.
355 Bosse et al., 2012; Herrero-Medrano et al., 2013; Silió et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2014), but
356 less commonly in other livestock species such as sheep (Al-Mamun et al., 2015; Beynon et
357 al., 2015; Muchadeyi et al., 2015). Al-Mamun et al. (2015) indicated that Border Leicester
358 breed has the largest total number of ROH, followed by Poll Dorset breed and finally, Merino

359 breed. These authors also identified ROH within autosomes. Beynon et al. (2015) used the
360 haplotype homozygosity method to infer population history and structure of Welsh sheep
361 breeds. This approach is based on the genome-wide distribution of ROH. Finally, Muchadeyi
362 et al. (2015) related the ROH regions with sub-vital performance in Swakara breed. In
363 addition, there have been relatively few studies assessing which set of parameters is optimal
364 for identifying ROH to better understand their effects on detecting inbreeding. Accordingly,
365 F_{ROH} does not accumulate over generations, as pedigree-based inbreeding estimates, because
366 ROH break down due to recombinations (Meuwissen et al., 2018). And lastly, the probability
367 of finding long ROH could be higher in regions surrounding the centromere, where the
368 recombination rate is supposed to be reduced. Then, efforts should be made to obtain correct
369 ROH-based inbreeding estimates when defining ROH. It has been shown that four defining
370 factors influence the identification of ROH-based inbreeding. The minimum length that
371 should constitute a ROH has been previously studied by Ferenčaković et al. (2013), who
372 considered a minimum length of 4 Mb to obtain reliable estimates of inbreeding. In addition,
373 ROH-based rates of inbreeding were higher with short ROH than with long ROH, in
374 agreement with results obtained from pedigree-based information in the same breeds (Buisson
375 et al., 2018). The minimum number of SNP that constituted a ROH is also an important ROH
376 defining factor. Accordingly, Forutan et al. (2018) indicated that a minimum ROH length of
377 20 to 50 SNP gave the most accurate and efficient estimates of ROH-based inbreeding
378 estimates. Other two important ROH defining factors identified in this study were the
379 maximum distance between two homozygous SNP and the minimum density between two
380 SNP. ROH-based rates of inbreeding in concordance to those obtained from pedigree-based
381 information require a specific set of values in the above ROH defining factors. This particular

382 set of values is different to that identified to obtain ROH-based rates of inbreeding similar to
383 those obtained on a SNP-by-SNP basis.

384

385 Detecting ROH based on 50K chip data was observed to give estimates similar to ROH from
386 sequence data (Zhang et al., 2015). Consequently, in the absence of full sequence data, ROH
387 based on 50K can be used to assess inbreeding. Notwithstanding, genotypes denser than 50K
388 could be required to accurately detect short ROH.

389

390 In conclusion, our results show that rates of inbreeding and effective population sizes are
391 empirically comparable across methods (pedigree, SNP-by-SNP and ROH). Effective
392 population sizes of these dairy sheep breeds are in the low hundreds. Also, factors to define
393 ROH do not change much the results unless extreme values are considered, although further
394 research on ROH-based inbreeding is still required.

395

396

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REFERENCES

- 406
407
- 408 Albrechtsen, A., F. C. Nielsen, and R. Nielsen. 2010. Ascertainment biases in SNP chips
409 affect measures of population divergence. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 27: 2534-2547.
- 410 Al-Mamun, H. A., S. A. Clark, P. Kwan, and C. Gondro. 2015. Genome-wide linkage
411 disequilibrium and genetic diversity in five populations of Australian domestic sheep.
412 *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 47: 90.
- 413 Baloché, G., A. Legarra, G. Sallé, H. Larroque, J. M. Astruc, C. Robert-Granié, and F.
414 Barillet. 2014. Assessment of accuracy of genomic prediction for French Lacaune dairy
415 sheep. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97: 1107-1116.
- 416 Beynon, S. E., G. T. Slavov, M. Farre, B. Sunduimijid, K. Waddams, B. Davies, W. Haresign,
417 J. Kijas, I. M. MacLeod, C. J. Newbold, L. Davies, and D. M. Larkin. 2015. Population
418 structure and history of the Welsh sheep breeds determined by whole genome
419 genotyping. *BMC Genet.* 16: 65.
- 420 Bjelland, D.W., K.A. Weigel, N. Vukasinovic, and J.D. Nkrumah. 2013. Evaluation of
421 inbreeding depression in Holstein cattle using whole-genome SNP markers and
422 alternative measures of genomic inbreeding. *J. Dairy Sci.* 96: 4697-4706.
- 423 Boichard, D. 2002. PEDIG: A Fortran package for pedigree analysis suited for large
424 populations. In *Proceedings of the 7th World Congress of Genetics Applied to*
425 *Livestock Production, France.*
- 426 Bosse, M., H.-J. Megens, O. Madsen, Y. Paudel, L.A. Frantz, L.B. Schook, R.P. Crooijmans,
427 and M.A. Groenen. 2012. Regions of homozygosity in the porcine genome:
428 consequence of demography and the recombination landscape. *PLoS Genet.* 8:
429 e1003100.

430 Broman, K., and J. L. Weber. 1999. Long homozygous chromosomal segments in reference
431 families from the Centre d'Etude du Polymorphisme Humain. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 65:
432 1493-500.

433 Buisson, D., J. M. Astruc, and F. Barillet. 2018. Bilan et perspectives de la gestion de la
434 variabilité génétique des ovins laitiers en France. *INRA Prod. Anim.* 31: 1-12.

435 Caballero, A., and M. A. Toro. 2002. Analysis of genetic diversity for the management of
436 conserved subdivided populations. *Conserv. Genet.* 3: 289-299.

437 Chitneedi, P. K., J. J. Arranz, A. Suarez-Vega, E. García-Gámez, and B. Gutiérrez-Gil. 2017.
438 Estimations of linkage disequilibrium, effective population size and ROH-based
439 inbreeding coefficients in Spanish Churra sheep using imputed high-density SNP
440 genotypes. *Anim. Genet.* 48: 436-446.

441 Curik, I., J. Sölkner, and N. Stipic. 2002. Effects of models with finite loci, selection,
442 dominance, epistasis and linkage on inbreeding coefficients based on pedigree and
443 genotypic information. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 119: 101-115.

444 Curik, I., M. Ferenčaković, and J. Sölkner. 2014. Inbreeding and runs of homozygosity: a
445 possible solution to an old problem. *Livest. Sci.* 166: 26-34.

446 Curtis, D., A.E. Vine, and J. Knight. 2008. Study of regions of extended homozygosity
447 provides a powerful method to explore haplotype structure of human populations. *Ann.*
448 *Hum. Genet.* 72: 261-278.

449 Daetwyler, H. D., B. Villanueva, P. Bijma, and J. A. Woolliams. 2007. Inbreeding in genome-
450 wide selection. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 124: 369-376.

451 Falconer, D. S., and T. F. C. Mackay. 1996. Introduction to quantitative genetics. Harlow:
452 Longman Scientific & Technical.

453 Ferenčakovič, M., E. Hamzic, B. Gredler, I. Curik, and J. Sölkner. 2011. Runs of
454 homozygosity reveal genome-wide autozygosity in the Austrian Fleckvieh cattle. *Agric.*
455 *Conspec. Sci.* 76: 325-328.

456 Ferenčaković, M., J. Sölkner, and I. Curik. 2013. Estimating autozygosity from high-
457 throughput information: effects of SNP density and genotyping errors. *Genet. Sel. Evol.*
458 45: 42.

459 Forutan, M., S. A. Mahyari, C. Baes, N. Melzer, F. S. Schenkel, and M. Sargolzaei. 2018.
460 Inbreeding and runs of homozygosity before and after genomic selection in North
461 American Holstein cattle. *BMC Genomics* 19: 98.

462 García-Cortés, L. A., A. Legarra, C. Chevalet, and M. A. Toro. 2013. Variance and
463 covariance of actual relationships between relatives at one locus. *PLoS ONE* 8: e57003.

464 García-Gómez, E., G. Sahana, B. Gutiérrez-Gil, and J. J. Arranz. 2012. Linkage
465 disequilibrium and inbreeding estimation in Spanish Churra sheep. *BMC Genet.* 13: 43.

466 Gibson, J., E. M. Newton, and A. Collins. 2006. Extended tracts of homozygosity in outbred
467 human populations. *Hum. Mol. Genet.* 15: 789-795.

468 Hayes, B. J., P. M. Visscher, H. C. McPartlan, and M. E. Goddard. 2003. Novel multilocus
469 measure of linkage disequilibrium to estimate past effective population size. *Genome*
470 *Res.* 13: 635-643.

471 Herrero-Medrano, J.M., H.-J. Megens, M.A.M. Groenen, G. Ramis, M. Bosse, M. Pérez-
472 Enciso, and R.P.M.A. Crooijmans. 2013. Conservation genomic analysis of domestic
473 and wild pig populations from the Iberian Peninsula. *BMC Genet.* 14: 106.

474 Hill, W. G., and B. S. Weir. 2011. Variation in actual relationship as a consequence of
475 Mendelian sampling and linkage. *Genet. Res.* 93: 47-64.

476 Howard, J. T., J. E. Pryce, C. Baes, and C. Maltecca. 2017. Invited review: Inbreeding in the
477 genomics era: Inbreeding, inbreeding depression, and management of genomic
478 variability. *J. Dairy Sci.* 100: 6009-6024.

479 Howrigan, D. P., M. A. Simonson, and M. C. Keller. 2011. Detecting autozygosity through
480 runs of homozygosity: a comparison of three autozygosity detection algorithms. *BMC*
481 *Genomics* 12: 460.

482 Keller, M. C., P. M. Visscher, and M. E. Goddard. 2011. Quantification of inbreeding due to
483 distant ancestors and its detection using dense single nucleotide polymorphism data.
484 *Genetics* 189: 237-249.

485 Kijas, J. W., J. A. Lenstra, B. Hayes, S. Boitard, L. R. Porto Neto, M. San Cristobal, B.
486 Servin, R. McCulloch, V. Whan, K. Gietzen, S. Paiva, W. Barendse, E. Ciani, H.
487 Raadsma, J. McEwan, B. Dalrymple, and other members of the International Sheep
488 Genomics Consortium. 2012. Genome-wide analysis of the World's sheep breeds
489 reveals high levels of historic mixture and strong recent selection. *PLoS Biol.* 10:
490 e1001258.

491 Kristensen, T. N., and A. C. Sorensen. 2005. Inbreeding-Lessons from animal breeding,
492 evolutionary biology and conservation genetics. *Anim. Sci.* 80: 121-133.

493 Ku, C. S., N. Naidoo, S. M. Teo, and Y. Pawitan. 2011. Regions of homozygosity and their
494 impact on complex diseases and traits. *Hum. Genet.* 129: 1-15.

495 Larroque, H., F. Barillet, G. Baloché, J. M. Astruc, D. Buisson, F. Shumbusho, V. Clément,
496 G. Lagriffoul, I. Palhiere, R. Rupp, C. Carillier, C. Robert-Granié, and A. Legarra.
497 2014. Toward genomic breeding programs in French dairy sheep and goats. In
498 *Proceedings of the 10th World Congress of Genetics Applied to Livestock Production,*
499 *Canada.*

500 Legarra, A., G. Baloche, F. Barillet, J. M. Astruc, C. Soulas, X. Aguerre, F. Arrese, L.
501 Mintegi, M. Lasarte, F. Maeztu, I. Beltrán de Heredia, and E. Ugarte. 2014. Within- and
502 across-breed genomic predictions and genomic relationships for Western Pyrenees dairy
503 sheep breeds Latxa, Manech, and Basco-Béarnaise. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97: 3200-3212.

504 Lencz, T., C. Lambert, P. DeRosse, K.E. Burdick, T.V. Morgan, J.M. Kane, R. Kucherlapati,
505 and A.K. Malhotra. 2007. Runs of homozygosity reveal highly penetrant recessive loci
506 in schizophrenia. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 104: 19942-19947.

507 Li, M. H., I. Strandén, and J. Kantanen. 2009. Genetic diversity and pedigree analysis of the
508 Finnsheep breed. *J. Anim. Sci.* 87: 1598-1605.

509 Malécot, G. 1948. *Les mathématiques de l'hérédité*. Paris: Masson & Cie.

510 Mastrangelo, S., B. Portolano, R. Di Gerlando, R. Ciampolini, M. Tolone, M. T. Sardina, and
511 International Sheep Genomics Consortium. 2017a. Genome-wide analysis in
512 endangered populations: a case study in Barbaresca sheep. *Animal* 11: 1107-1116.

513 Mastrangelo, S., M. Tolone, M. T. Sardina, G. Sottile, A. M. Sutura, R. Di Gerlando, and B.
514 Portolano. 2017b. Genome-wide scan for runs of homozygosity identifies potential
515 candidate genes associated with local adaptation in Valle del Belice sheep. *Genet. Sel.*
516 *Evol.* 49: 84.

517 Mastrangelo, S., M. Tolone, R. D. Gerlando, L. Fontanesi, M. T. Sardina, and B. Portolano.
518 2016. Genomic inbreeding estimation in small populations: evaluation of runs of
519 homozygosity in three local dairy cattle breeds. *Animal* 10: 746-754.

520 McQuillan, R., A. Leutenegger, R. Abdel-Rahman, C. S. Franklin, M. Pericic, L. Barac-Lauc,
521 N. Smolej-Narancic, B. Janicijevic, O. Polasek, A. Tenesa, A. K. Macleod, S. M.
522 Farrington, P. Rudan, C. Hayward, V. Vitart, I. Rudan, S. H. Wild, M. G. Dunlop, A. F.

523 Wright, H. Campbell, and J. F. Wilson. 2008. Runs of homozygosity in European
524 populations. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 83: 359-372.

525 Meuwissen, T. H. E. 1997. Maximizing the response of selection with a predefined rate of
526 inbreeding. *J. Anim. Sci.* 75: 934-940.

527 Meuwissen, T. H. E. 2009. Genetic management of small populations: a review. *Acta Agric.*
528 *Scand. A Anim. Sci.* 59: 71-79.

529 Meuwissen, T. H. E., A. K. Sonesson, and J. A. Woolliams. 2018. Genomic management of
530 inbreeding in breeding schemes. In *Proceedings of the 11th World Congress of Genetics*
531 *Applied to Livestock Production, New Zealand.*

532 Meuwissen, T. H. E., and Z. Luo. 1992. Computing inbreeding coefficients in large
533 populations. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 24: 305-313.

534 Muchadeyi, F. C., M. T. Malesa, P. Soma, and E. F. Dzomba. 2015. Runs of homozygosity in
535 Swakara pelt producing sheep: implications on sub-vital performance. In *Proceedings of*
536 *the AAABG 21: 310-313.*

537 Oliehoek, P. A., and P. Bijma. 2009. Effects of pedigree errors on the efficiency of
538 conservation decisions. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 41: 9.

539 Peripolli, E., D. P. Munari, M. V. G. B. Silva, A. L. F. Lima, R. Irgang, and F. Baldi. 2017.
540 Runs of homozygosity: current knowledge and applications in livestock. *Anim. Genet.*
541 48: 255-271.

542 Purfield, D. C., D. Berry, S. McParland, and D. G. Bradley. 2012. Runs of homozygosity and
543 population history in cattle. *BMC Genet.* 13: 70.

544 Purfield, D. C., S. McParland, E. Wall, and D. P. Berry. 2017. The distribution of runs of
545 homozygosity and selection signatures in six commercial meat sheep breeds. *PLoS*
546 *ONE* 12: e0176780.

547 Silió, L., M. C. Rodríguez, A. Fernández, C. Barragán, R. Benítez, C. Óvilo, A. I. Fernández.
548 2013. Measuring inbreeding and inbreeding depression on pig growth from pedigree or
549 SNP-derived metrics. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 130: 349-360.

550 Smith, J. M., and J. Haigh. 1974. The hitch-hiking effect of a favourable gene. *Genet. Res.* 23:
551 23-35.

552 Sonesson, A. K., J. A. Woolliams, and T. H. E. Meuwissen. 2012. Genomic selection requires
553 genomic control of inbreeding. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 44: 27.

554 Toro, M. A., L. A. García-Cortés, and A. Legarra. 2011. A note on the rationale for estimating
555 genealogical coancestry from molecular markers. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 43: 27.

556 Tortereau, F., C. R. Moreno, G. Tosser-Klopp, B. Servin, and J. Raoul. 2017. Development of
557 a SNP panel dedicated to parentage assignment in French sheep populations. *BMC*
558 *Genet.* 18: 50.

559 VanRaden, P. M. 2008. Efficient methods to compute genomic predictions. *J. Dairy Sc.* 91:
560 4414-4423.

561 Wang, J. 2005. Estimation of effective population sizes from data on genetic markers. *Philos.*
562 *Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B Biol. Sci.* 360: 1395-1409.

563 Wright, S. 1922. Coefficients of inbreeding and relationship. *Am. Nat.* 56: 330-338.

564 Zhang, Q., B. Guldbrandtsen, M. Bosse, X. Sun, A. Wolc, and J. C. M. Dekkers. 2015. Runs
565 of homozygosity and distribution of functional variants in the cattle genome. *BMC*
566 *Genomics* 16: 542.

567 Zhang, Y., J.M. Young, C. Wang, X. Sun, A. Wolc, and J.C.M. Dekkers. 2014. Inbreeding by
568 pedigree and genomic markers in selection lines of pigs. In *Proceedings of the 10th*
569 *World Congress of Genetics Applied to Livestock Production, Canada.*

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APPENDIX

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576 **Supplementary Figure 1.** Distribution of the genotyped rams per year of birth. BB: Basco-

577 Béarnaise, MTN: Manech Tête Noire, MTR: Manech Tête Rousse, LACCon: Lacaune

578 Confederation, LACOvi: Lacaune Ovitest.

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583 **Supplementary Figure 2.** Evolution of the rate of inbreeding per generation (ΔF) in relation

584 with the maximum number of missing genotypes and the maximum number of heterozygous.

585 BB: Basco-Béarnaise, MTN: Manech Tête Noire, MTR: Manech Tête Rousse, LACCon:

586 Lacaune Confederation, LACOvi: Lacaune Ovitest. Grey point indicates the default value.

587 Bars indicate the standard error. Dashed line indicates the 95% confidence interval of

588 pedigree-based inbreeding. Dotted line indicates the 95% confidence interval of SNP-by-

589 SNP-based inbreeding.

590

FIGURE LEGENDS

591

592 **Figure 1.** Example of run of homozygosity within the dotted squares. The first allele is
593 indicated by 1 and the second allele is indicated by 2 within the circles. The minimum length
594 that constituted a ROH was 4 Mb, the minimum number of SNP was 10, the minimum density
595 was 1 SNP per 10 Kb, the maximum distance allowed between two consecutive homozygous
596 SNP in a run was 1 Mb, a maximum of two missing genotypes were allowed (empty circles)
597 and one heterozygous genotype within a particular ROH was permitted (alleles indicated in
598 black). n_{ROH} refers to the number of ROH, l_{ROH} indicates the length of the ROH and l_g is the
599 length of the genome.

600

601 **Figure 2.** Evolution of the rate of inbreeding per generation (ΔF) in relation to the minimum
602 length that constituted a ROH (Mb). BB: Basco-Béarnaise, MTN: Manech Tête Noire, MTR:
603 Manech Tête Rousse, LACCon: Lacaune Confederation, LACOvi: Lacaune Ovitest. Grey
604 point indicates the default value. Bars indicate the standard error. Dashed line indicates the
605 95% confidence interval of pedigree-based inbreeding. Dotted line indicates the 95%
606 confidence interval of SNP-by-SNP-based inbreeding.

607

608 **Figure 3.** Evolution of the rate of inbreeding per generation (ΔF) in relation to the minimum
609 number of SNP, the minimum density and the maximum distance between 2 homozygous
610 SNP. BB: Basco-Béarnaise, MTN: Manech Tête Noire, MTR: Manech Tête Rousse,
611 LACCon: Lacaune Confederation, LACOvi: Lacaune Ovitest. Grey point indicates the default
612 value. Bars indicate the standard error. Dashed line indicates the 95% confidence interval of

613 pedigree-based inbreeding. Dotted line indicates the 95% confidence interval of SNP-by-

614 SNP-based inbreeding.

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618 **Table 1.** Number of genotyped animals, individuals included in the pedigree and equivalent
619 number of complete generations per subpopulation and breed. BB: Basco-Béarnaise, MTN:
620 Manech Tête Noire, MTR: Manech Tête Rousse, LACCon: Lacaune Confederation, LACovi:
621 Lacaune Ovitest.

622

	Genotyped individuals	Individuals in pedigree	Equivalent number of complete generations
BB	321	1,861	6.10
MTN	329	1,616	5.29
MTR	1,906	11,574	7.61
LACCon	3,030	29,255	10.84
LACovi	3,114	28,497	11.69

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626 **Table 2.** Values tested for each ROH defining factor. In bold the default values.

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Factor	Tested values										
Minimum length ROH (Mb)	0.2	1	2	4	6	8	10	12	16	18	20
Minimum number SNP	15	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	100	500	1000
Minimum density (at least 1 SNP every this number of bases, Kb)	5	10	20	30	40	50	70	90	100	150	200
Maximum distance between 2 homozygous SNP (Mb)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.8	1	2	4	6
Maximum number of missing genotypes	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	10	12	14
Maximum number of heterozygous	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	10	12	14

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636 **Table 3.** Mean (F) \pm standard error (SE) of the inbreeding coefficient, rate of inbreeding per
637 generation (ΔF) \pm SE and effective population size (N_e) (95% confidence interval, CI) for
638 each evaluated subpopulation and breed. BB: Basco-Béarnaise, MTN: Manech Tête Noire,
639 MTR: Manech Tête Rousse, LACCon: Lacaune Confederation, LACOvi: Lacaune Ovitest.
640 F_{PED} : inbreeding calculated from pedigree-based information, F_{SNP} : inbreeding calculated on
641 a SNP-by-SNP basis, F_{ROH} : ROH-based inbreeding.

642

		Breed or subpopulation				
		BB	MTN	MTR	LACCon	LACOvi
Mean \pm SE						
	F_{PED}	0.0296 \pm 0.0009	0.0298 \pm 0.0010	0.0239 \pm 0.0003	0.0234 \pm 0.0002	0.0311 \pm 0.0002
	F_{SNP}	0.6294 \pm 0.0005	0.6300 \pm 0.0006	0.6226 \pm 0.0002	0.6202 \pm 0.0001	0.6230 \pm 0.0001
	F_{ROH}^*	0.0379 \pm 0.0012	0.0440 \pm 0.0013	0.0368 \pm 0.0004	0.0346 \pm 0.0003	0.0407 \pm 0.0003
$\Delta F \pm$ SE						
	ΔF_{PED}	0.0099 \pm 0.0017	0.0094 \pm 0.0012	0.0045 \pm 0.0004	0.0019 \pm 0.0002	0.0022 \pm 0.0002
	ΔF_{SNP}	0.0044 \pm 0.0010	0.0028 \pm 0.0007	0.0025 \pm 0.0002	0.0016 \pm 0.0001	0.0014 \pm 0.0001
	ΔF_{ROH}^*	0.0085 \pm 0.0024	0.0062 \pm 0.0017	0.0046 \pm 0.0006	0.0022 \pm 0.0003	0.0014 \pm 0.0003
N_e (95% CI)						
	N_{ePED}	51 (38 - 76)	53 (43 - 71)	111 (95 - 135)	263 (218 - 332)	227 (193 - 277)
	N_{eSNP}	114 (79 - 205)	179 (120 - 350)	200 (173 - 237)	313 (278 - 356)	357 (313 - 415)
	N_{eROH}^*	59 (38 - 132)	81 (52 - 174)	109 (87 - 146)	227 (179 - 310)	357 (252 - 616)

643

644 * ROH identifying values were: (i) the minimum length that constituted a ROH was 4 Mb; (ii)
645 the minimum number of SNP was 30; (iii) the minimum density was 1 SNP per 100 Kb; (iv)
646 the maximum distance allowed between two consecutive homozygous SNP in a run was 1
647 Mb; (v) a maximum of two missing genotypes and (vi) one heterozygous genotype within a
648 particular ROH were permitted.

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651 **Table 4.** Correlation coefficient of the inbreeding estimates for each evaluated subpopulation
652 and breed. BB: Basco-Béarnaise, MTN: Manech Tête Noire, MTR: Manech Tête Rousse,
653 LACCon: Lacaune Confederation, LACOvi: Lacaune Ovitest. F_{PED} : inbreeding calculated
654 from pedigree-based information, F_{SNP} : inbreeding calculated on a SNP-by-SNP basis, F_{ROH} :
655 ROH-based inbreeding.

656

	F_{PED} vs F_{SNP}	F_{PED} vs F_{ROH}^*	F_{SNP} vs F_{ROH}^*
BB	0.53	0.51	0.86
MTN	0.50	0.48	0.88
MTR	0.56	0.58	0.84
LACCon	0.38	0.38	0.78
LACOvi	0.42	0.40	0.79

657

658 * ROH identifying values were: (i) the minimum length that constituted a ROH was 4 Mb; (ii)
659 the minimum number of SNP was 30; (iii) the minimum density was 1 SNP per 100 Kb; (iv)
660 the maximum distance allowed between two consecutive homozygous SNP in a run was 1
661 Mb; (v) a maximum of two missing genotypes and (vi) one heterozygous genotype within a
662 particular ROH were permitted.

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685 **Figure 2**
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691 **Figure 3**
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BB

MTN

MTR

LACCon

LACovi

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